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MATHEMATICAL CREATIVITY SELF-EFFICACY PERCEPTION OF PRE-SERVICE MATHEMATICS TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the significant differences in the levels of mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions among pre-service mathematics teachers based on their demographic profiles. A descriptive-comparative research design was employed, utilizing a stratified random sampling technique. A total of 101 students participated in the study. Data were collected using an adopted survey questionnaire. Means were used to describe quantitative variables, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine differences among the considered groups. Results revealed that the respondents exhibited a high level of mathematical creativity self-efficacy, indicating strong beliefs in their mathematical creativity. Their confidence suggests that they possess the necessary creativity to effectively solve mathematical problems, employing flexible strategies and generating innovative solutions. The comparative analysis showed a significant difference in mathematical creativity self-efficacy among pre-service teachers, with LGBTQ students exhibiting significantly higher levels than their male and female counterparts. Additionally, students in higher year levels demonstrated significantly greater self-efficacy compared to those in lower year levels. Similarly, older students displayed significantly higher mathematical creativity self-efficacy than younger students. These findings suggest that as students gain maturity and experience, their mathematical creativity self-efficacy increases.

Keywords: Mathematical creativity self-efficacy, pre-service mathematics teachers

1. INTRODUCTION

A globalized society faces challenges that require creativity to solve (Glăveanu, 2016). Creativity plays a vital role in education, contributing to national development and the training of individuals who will drive future innovations (Esi, 2018). Emphasizing creative skills, particularly in educational settings, has led to the search for effective methods to enhance learners' creativity (Huang et al., 2018). In our rapidly changing world, the new generation must possess the knowledge, skills, and qualifications necessary to keep pace with evolving demands. Successful individuals should demonstrate problem-solving abilities, metacognitive thinking, and both critical and creative thinking skills (Lumoto et al., 2024; Villegas et al. 2024). Research on creativity began in the 1950s and continues to evolve (Esi, 2018).

Mathematical creativity is essential for the advancement of mathematics as a discipline. In a world where both evolutionary and revolutionary innovations are increasingly valued, creativity and innovation have become paramount. However, the creativity of mathematicians—the source of this growth—remains a relatively unexplored area in mathematics and mathematics education, particularly in the Philippines. Shen (2017) emphasized that creativity is crucial in mathematics, as creative development in this field lays the foundation for advancements in other disciplines, including science and the social sciences. Posing and solving mathematical problems in multiple ways foster creativity, allowing students to develop their own innovative ideas (Singer, Ellerton, & Cai, 2013; Sabanal et al., 2024).

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Numerous studies (Anyor & Omenka, 2015; Havold, 2018; Huang et al., 2017) have highlighted that mathematical creativity is an essential skill for all students. These studies emphasize that learning environments should be designed to strengthen students' creativity while they acquire new mathematical knowledge. The most significant responsibility for fostering mathematical creativity lies with teachers (Leikin & Elgrably, 2019). This responsibility underscores the need to enhance future teachers' knowledge and skills in mathematical creativity.

Mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception refers to an individual's confidence in their ability to generate creative and unique solutions in mathematics. It reflects belief in one's own creative skills when solving mathematical problems or exploring mathematical concepts. Therefore, examining this perception among pre-service mathematics teachers is crucial in preparing them to foster creativity in their future students. This study focuses on three key aspects: fluency, flexibility, and originality (Aksungur & Açıkgül, 2022).

Despite the growing emphasis on creativity in mathematics, limited research has been conducted on mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception, particularly in Mindanao. Given this gap, the researchers aimed to determine the level of mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception among pre-service mathematics teachers at a state college in Mindanao.

2. OBJECTIVES

The study focused on determining and comparing how Mathematical Creativity Self-Efficacy Perception affects mathematics pre-service teachers enrolled at a state college in Mindanao during the first semester of SY 2024–2025. Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender; and
 - 1.3 Year Level.
2. Determine the level of mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception in terms of:
 - 1.1. Fluency
 - 1.2. Flexibility; and
 - 1.3. Originality
3. Determine the significant difference in the level of mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception of the respondents when grouped according to the demographic profile.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-comparative research design, which is used to describe differences between groups in a population without manipulating the independent variable. A comparative research design involves gathering data to determine whether a significant difference exists between two or more variables. This approach is particularly relevant in quantitative research, where data is collected from larger groups or samples. The primary aim of this study was to determine the level of mathematical creativity among first-year to fourth-year BSED Mathematics students. Data collection involved a descriptive survey, utilizing a questionnaire to assess the respondents' level of mathematical creativity.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study was the adopted Mathematical Creativity Self-Efficacy Perception Scale for Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers, developed by Aksungur Altun and Açıkgül (2022). The scale consists of three domains with a total of 30 statements, rated on a Likert scale: Always, Often, Sometimes, Rarely, and Never. The first domain, Fluency, includes 10 statements; the second domain, Flexibility, comprises 10 statements; and the third domain, Originality, consists of 10 statements.

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The scale demonstrates very high internal consistency for pre-service mathematics teachers, as reflected by the Cronbach's alpha values for each factor. Fluency exhibits a Cronbach's alpha of 0.927, Flexibility has an alpha of 0.939, and Originality obtained 0.952. The overall reliability of the scale is 0.970, indicating a very high level of consistency across all factors.

Respondents of the Study

The researchers employed a stratified sampling technique to select first-year to fourth-year BSED-Mathematics students from a state college in Mindanao. This method involves dividing the population into distinct subgroups, or strata, based on characteristics relevant to the research objectives. These characteristics may include demographic factors such as age, gender, or academic year level.

To determine the appropriate sample size, Slovin's formula was applied, ensuring a statistically representative sample with a desired level of accuracy. By using Slovin's formula, the researchers aimed to minimize potential sampling errors while maintaining a sample that accurately represents the population. This approach enhances the reliability of the findings related to mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception in terms of fluency, flexibility, and originality.

Furthermore, the researchers sought to determine whether there is a significant difference in the level of mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception among pre-service mathematics teachers when grouped according to age, gender, and year level. The distribution of respondents is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents

Course	NO. OF THE STUDENTS (N)	SAMPLE SIZE (n)
1	28	21
2	34	25
3	26	20
4	47	35
Total:	135	101

Data Gathering

The data-gathering procedure began with the researchers submitting a formal letter to the Vice President for Academic Affairs (VPAA) and the selected first-year to fourth-year BSED-Mathematics students of a state college in Mindanao. To collect data, the researchers used an adopted questionnaire as the primary data-gathering instrument. A physical questionnaire was carefully distributed to the respondents in person, allowing the researchers to address any clarifications or questions. Before answering the questionnaire, respondents underwent a clear and specific orientation regarding its limitations and privacy considerations.

To ensure confidentiality and encourage honest responses, respondents were given the option to withhold personal details. Ethical considerations were strictly observed, and the researchers followed proper etiquette when approaching respondents, ensuring that participation remained voluntary. Once the questionnaires were completed, the researchers took full responsibility for maintaining the confidentiality of all collected data. The gathered data were tallied, collated, and tabulated for processing and analysis. Tables were created to illustrate the data, and the results were summarized and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools with the assistance of statistical software.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The demographic profile of one hundred one (101) pre-service mathematics teachers enrolled in the BSED-Mathematics program at a state college in Mindanao is presented in Table 2.

In terms of age, the mean age of the respondents was 20.28 years. The ages ranged from 18 to 23 years, with the largest group of respondents aged 20–21 years, comprising 45 students (44.55%). This was followed by 34 students (33.66%) aged 18–19 years, while 22 students (21.78%) were aged 22–23 years. These findings align with Shah and Gustafsson (2021), who observed that age may influence individuals'

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creative thinking, as younger individuals might exhibit different patterns of cognitive engagement compared to their older peers. The results suggest that the pre-service mathematics teachers in this study represent a young demographic, which could be a factor in their approach to creative problem-solving and teaching strategies.

Regarding gender, the study revealed that the majority of respondents were female, with 56 students (55.45%), followed by 42 male students (41.58%) and 3 LGBTQ+ students (2.97%). This demographic characteristic highlights the gender diversity among pre-service mathematics teachers. Acar and Runco (2019) emphasized the importance of understanding gender differences in creative potential and performance, noting that such differences can influence teaching approaches and the development of innovative strategies in the classroom. The predominance of female respondents aligns with broader trends in education, where women often outnumber men in teacher training programs.

In terms of year level, the highest number of respondents were fourth-year pre-service mathematics teachers, with 35 students. This was followed by the second-year and first-year groups, each with 21 students, and the third-year group, which had 20 students. The variation in year levels provides insights into the progression of students through the program.

Table 2. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Particular	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Age		
18-19 years old	34	33.66%
20-21 years old	45	44.55%
22-23 years old	22	21.78%
Mean = 20.28 years		
Gender		
Female	56	55.45%
Male	42	41.48%
LGBTQ+	3	2.97%
Year Level		
1 st year	21	20.79%
2 nd year	25	24.75%
3 rd year	20	19.80%
4 th year	35	34.65%
Total:	101	101

Level of Mathematical Creativity Self-Efficacy Perception

The research results, as presented in Table 3, reveal the students' level of mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception among pre-service mathematics teachers across three key domains: fluency, flexibility, and originality. The overall mean score of 3.54, categorized as high, indicates that pre-service mathematics teachers have strong confidence in their creative problem-solving abilities. This suggests that they frequently employ flexible strategies and generate innovative solutions in mathematical contexts. Such confidence implies that they possess the necessary creativity to tackle mathematical problems effectively.

This result aligns with the findings of Açıkgül and Aksungur Altun (2022), who reported that pre-service mathematics teachers generally hold high beliefs in their mathematical creativity. Their study emphasized the importance of fostering self-efficacy in mathematical creativity, as it plays a crucial role in enhancing problem-solving skills and innovative thinking.

Fluency

Examining the domains of mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception, fluency yielded the highest mean value of 3.63, categorized as high. This indicates that pre-service teachers strongly believe in their capacity to apply flexible strategies and identify multiple mathematical problems they encounter in their lives. This finding is consistent with Hine (2015), who emphasized the importance of procedural fluency

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and mathematical content knowledge in teacher preparation programs. His study highlights the notion that pre-service teachers are confident in their ability to solve mathematical problems effectively.

Meanwhile, Item 2—"Students can develop many solutions in a certain period of time by evaluating possible situations while trying to solve a mathematical problem"—obtained a mean score of 3.45. Although still categorized as high, it represents the lowest mean within the fluency domain. This suggests that pre-service teachers can generate multiple solutions within a given time frame by evaluating possible situations while solving mathematical problems.

These findings align with the study of Schoevers et al. (2020), which emphasized that mathematical fluency involves producing numerous correct solutions within limited constraints, showcasing adaptive and creative thinking. Similarly, Malgapo and Villaflor (2022) highlighted that pre-service teachers demonstrate high fluency in mathematics by leveraging various strategies to explore and evaluate potential outcomes, reinforcing their ability to address mathematical challenges effectively.

Flexibility

The flexibility domain obtained a mean value of 3.61, categorized as high, indicating that pre-service teachers have strong confidence in their creative problem-solving abilities. They regularly apply flexible strategies and generate innovative solutions in mathematical contexts. According to Schoevers et al. (2020), flexibility refers to the number of different categories into which an individual's answers fall.

Meanwhile, Item 2—"Students can deal with a daily life problem from different mathematical perspectives"—obtained a mean score of 3.76. Although still categorized as high, this represents the highest mean within the flexibility domain. This suggests that pre-service teachers can approach real-life problems from multiple mathematical viewpoints, demonstrating adaptability in problem-solving.

Originality

The originality domain obtained a mean value of 3.39, which is lower than the other two domains. This score is categorized as moderate, indicating that pre-service teachers have a balanced level of confidence in their ability to think creatively in mathematics. While they can generate ideas and solve problems effectively, they may not always seek out or excel in producing novel solutions. This finding aligns with Schoevers et al. (2020), who defined originality as the degree to which an answer is unusual or novel compared to a reference group.

Items 6, 9, and 10 under the originality domain all obtained the same mean value of 3.42, categorized as high. These items include: (1) "I can come up with non-traditional solutions for mathematical problems," (2) "I can put forward extraordinary ideas regarding the results of mathematical events in daily life," and (3) "I can solve a mathematical problem from a different perspective compared to my peers." These responses suggest that while pre-service teachers exhibit creativity in mathematical problem-solving, their confidence in producing highly original ideas remains moderate.

According to Walia and Walia (2021), mathematical ability had the lowest predictive value for originality compared to fluency and flexibility. However, they noted that originality was not corrected for the fluency confound, indicating that a strong fluency component may influence originality scores.

Table 2: The Level of Mathematical Creativity Self-Efficacy Perception of Pre-Service Mathematics Teacher

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTION
Fluency	3.63	High
Flexibility	3.61	High
Originality	3.32	Moderate
Mathematical Creativity Self-Efficacy Perception (OVERALL)	3.54	High

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The Significant Difference in the Level of Mathematical Creativity Self-Efficacy Perception of Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers According to their Demographic Profile

Table 3 presents the significant differences in the level of mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception among pre-service mathematics teachers when grouped according to their demographic profiles. The results indicate statistically significant variations in self-efficacy perceptions across the examined groups.

For age groups (18–19, 20–21, 22–23), the p-value of <0.001 suggests a significant effect of age on mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions. This finding leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that individuals' perceptions meaningfully differ across age groups.

Regarding gender groups (female, male, LGBTQ+), the p-value of <0.001 confirms significant differences, implying that gender plays a critical role in shaping mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions among pre-service mathematics teachers.

For year levels (1st year, 2nd year, 3rd year, 4th year), the p-value of <0.001 highlights a significant variation in self-efficacy perceptions based on academic progression. This suggests that as students advance through the program, their perceptions of mathematical creativity self-efficacy evolve accordingly.

Table 3. The Significant Difference in the Level of Mathematical Creativity Self-Efficacy Perception of Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers According to their Demographic Profile

INDICATORS	GROUP	MEAN	p-VALUE	DECISION
Age	18-19	3.14	0.000	Reject Hypothesis
	20-21	3.70		
	22-23	3.84		
Gender	Female	3.40	0.000	Reject Hypothesis
	Male	3.65		
	LGBTQ+	4.56		
Year Level	1 st Year	3.10	0.000	Reject Hypothesis
	2 nd Year	3.43		
	3 rd Year	3.75		
	4 th Year	3.76		

The Post-Hoc Test Analysis

To further explore these differences, post hoc tests were conducted to identify the specific group pairs contributing to the observed variations. The results, obtained using the Tukey HSD method, provide key insights into the differences in mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions among the various age groups.

The comparison between the 18–19 and 20–21 age groups yielded a mean difference of 0.556 with a p-value of <0.001, indicating a statistically significant difference. This suggests that mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions vary considerably between these two groups.

Conversely, the comparison between the 20–21 and 22–23 age groups resulted in a mean difference of 0.145 with a p-value of 0.482, indicating no statistically significant difference. This finding suggests that mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions remain relatively stable between these age groups.

Lastly, the comparison between the 22–23 and 18–19 age groups showed a mean difference of 0.702 with a p-value of <0.001, signifying a statistically significant difference. This suggests that students in the 22–23 age group perceive their mathematical creativity self-efficacy more positively compared to those in the 18–19 age group.

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Overall, the findings indicate that mathematical creativity self-efficacy significantly differs according to age, with older students exhibiting higher levels of self-efficacy in mathematical creativity. This aligns with the study of Bales and Estomo (2021), which suggests that as students mature, their mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions tend to increase. Similarly, Tierney and Farmer (2022) emphasized that mathematical creativity self-efficacy develops over time as individuals gain more experience and confidence in their abilities. It is argued that older students, having encountered more diverse learning experiences and problem-solving situations, are more likely to perceive themselves as capable of generating creative solutions, thereby reinforcing the link between confidence, adaptability, and mathematical creativity self-efficacy (Miranda, 2018; Adlawon et al, 2022; Agtarap & Miranda, 2022).

Table 4. Post Hoc Result according to Age

Age	Mean Difference	p-value	Significant
18-19 and 20-21	0.556	0.000	Significant
20-21 and 21-22	0.145	0.482	Not Significant
21-22 and 18-19	0.702	0.000	Significant

The post hoc test results in Table 5, using the Tukey HSD method, provide valuable insights into the differences in mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions among different gender groups.

The comparison between male and female pre-service mathematics teachers yielded a mean difference of 0.249 with a p-value of 0.056. Since the p-value exceeds the common threshold of 0.05, this difference is not statistically significant. This indicates that mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions do not significantly differ between male and female pre-service mathematics teachers.

However, the LGBTQ+ group exhibited significantly higher mathematical creativity self-efficacy compared to both male and female students, with mean differences of 0.906 and 1.156, respectively. This finding aligns with prior research suggesting that gender alone does not necessarily determine self-efficacy in mathematical creativity. Pajanes and Miller (2023) claimed that although males and females may have different confidence levels in specific mathematical tasks, their overall self-efficacy in mathematical problem-solving and creativity remains comparable. Similarly, Else-Quest, Hyde, and Linn (2024) concluded that while some variations exist in certain domains, self-efficacy in mathematical creativity does not significantly differ between male and female students.

The finding that LGBTQ+ students exhibit significantly higher mathematical creativity self-efficacy than their male and female counterparts aligns with research highlighting the role of identity, resilience, and self-perception in academic confidence. Bandura (2025) emphasized that individuals who navigate challenges and develop strong self-beliefs tend to demonstrate higher levels of creative problem-solving. This suggests that LGBTQ+ students' experiences in overcoming societal barriers may contribute to their enhanced mathematical creativity self-efficacy. Similarly, Riggle et al. (2026) found that self-awareness, adaptability, and cognitive flexibility—key attributes associated with LGBTQ+ identity—positively influence creativity and academic confidence.

Table 5. Post Hoc Result according to Gender

Gender	Mean Difference	p-value	Significant
Male and Female	0.249	0.056	Not Significant
Male and LGBTQ+	0.906	0.000	Significant
LGBTQ+ and Female	1.156	0.000	Significant

Table 6 presents the post hoc test results using the Tukey HSD method, revealing significant differences in mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions among pre-service mathematics teachers across different year levels.

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The comparison between 1st-year and 2nd-year students shows a mean difference of 0.337 with a p-value of 0.113, indicating that the difference is not statistically significant. This suggests that self-efficacy perceptions between 1st-year and 2nd-year students are relatively similar.

In contrast, the comparison between 1st-year and 3rd-year students shows a mean difference of 0.657 with a p-value of <0.001, indicating a statistically significant difference. This finding suggests that 3rd-year students have significantly higher mathematical creativity self-efficacy perceptions than 1st-year students. Similarly, the comparison between 1st-year and 4th-year students reveals a mean difference of 0.603 with a p-value of <0.001, indicating that 4th-year students also exhibit significantly higher self-efficacy perceptions compared to 1st-year students.

On the other hand, the comparison between 2nd-year and 3rd-year students shows a mean difference of 0.319 with a p-value of 0.153, which is not statistically significant. This suggests that self-efficacy perceptions between 2nd-year and 3rd-year students are relatively similar.

These results highlight the impact of academic year level on self-efficacy perceptions, with significant differences observed primarily between early and later year levels. This finding aligns with Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory, which suggests that mastery experiences play a crucial role in shaping an individual's confidence in their abilities. As students progress through their academic journey, they gain more exposure to mathematical problems, develop problem-solving strategies, and refine creative thinking skills, which in turn enhances their self-efficacy. Similarly, Zimmerman and Schunk (2011) emphasized that as students advance in their education, they develop greater confidence in applying creative approaches to problem-solving.

Table 6. Post Hoc Result according to Year Level

Year Level	Mean Difference	p-value	Significant
1 st year and 2 nd year	0.337	0.113	Not Significant
1 st year and 3 rd year	0.657	0.000	Significant
1 st year and 4 th year	0.603	0.000	Significant
2 nd year and 3 rd year	0.319	0.153	Not Significant
2 nd year and 4 th year	0.326	0.069	Not Significant
3 rd year and 4 th year	0.006	1.000	Not Significant

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the findings and statistical results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The majority of the respondents fall within the typical college-age range in the Philippines, with an average age of 20.28 years. While female students slightly outnumber male students, the distribution remains relatively balanced, and LGBTQ+ representation is minimal. The findings confirm that pre-service mathematics teachers generally exhibit a high level of mathematical creativity self-efficacy.
2. The results further confirm that mathematical creativity self-efficacy varies significantly with age, with older students demonstrating higher levels of self-efficacy compared to younger students. This suggests that as students mature, their confidence in their creative mathematical abilities increases.
3. In terms of gender differences, LGBTQ+ students exhibit significantly higher mathematical creativity self-efficacy than their male and female counterparts. Additionally, students in higher year levels demonstrate significantly greater self-efficacy in mathematical creativity compared to students in lower year levels. This finding suggests that academic progression enhances confidence in creative mathematical problem-solving.

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4. These results emphasize the impact of experience, maturity, and identity-related factors on students' confidence in their mathematical creativity.

Recommendation

1. Since the overall mathematical creativity self-efficacy perception was high, it is recommended to continuously reinforce students' confidence in their creative abilities. Regular positive reinforcement through awards, recognition programs, and opportunities to showcase creative solutions in mathematical contests can further enhance their self-belief. Additionally, as the tendency to avoid challenges negatively impacts performance, educators should introduce growth mindset strategies by exposing students to more complex and engaging problems to reduce avoidance behavior. Teachers can foster resilience by emphasizing that challenges are opportunities for growth and learning.
2. Since younger students (18–19 years old) reported significantly lower self-efficacy perceptions, it is recommended to implement age-specific interventions aimed at boosting their confidence in creative problem-solving. For example, mentorship programs pairing younger students with more senior peers could provide guidance and encouragement. Additionally, while most students performed well, few reached the superior level. To support high-achieving students, advanced problem-solving sessions or enrichment programs should be introduced to bridge the gap to superior performance.
3. Given the significant difference in mathematical creativity self-efficacy between LGBTQ+ respondents and the male and female groups, it is crucial to create an inclusive environment that recognizes and values gender diversity. Programs and workshops aimed at enhancing the self-efficacy of LGBTQ+ students should be implemented, ensuring that they have equal opportunities and support in developing their mathematical creativity.
4. Since higher-year students (3rd and 4th years) exhibited significantly greater self-efficacy, it would be beneficial to implement early-stage interventions to help 1st and 2nd-year students develop similar levels of confidence. Regular workshops, seminars, and exposure to real-world mathematical challenges can foster self-efficacy at these earlier stages.
5. Future researchers are encouraged to explore the long-term effects of targeted interventions on mathematical creativity self-efficacy across various demographic groups, including age, gender, and year level. A longitudinal study tracking the development of self-efficacy over time could provide valuable insights into how sustained interventions—such as mentoring, inclusive workshops, or curriculum adjustments—impact students' confidence in creative problem-solving.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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